

Analysis of the relationships among infrastructure, operation, safety, and environment aspects that influence public transport users: Case study of university small and medium sized cities in Brazil

This document is a **post-print version** (i.e. final draft post-refereeing) of the following paper:

Ruiz-Padillo, A. and De Oña, J. (2024) Analysis of the relationships among infrastructure, operation, safety, and environment aspects that influence public transport users: Case study of university small and medium sized cities in Brazil. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, *in press*. DOI: 10.1016/j.tra.2024.104115

Direct access to the published version: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2024.104115>

Analysis of the relationships among infrastructure, operation, safety, and environment aspects that influence public transport users: Case study of university small and medium sized cities in Brazil

Alejandro Ruiz-Padillo^{a,b,*}

Juan de Oña^b

^aMobility and Logistics Laboratory. Federal University of de Santa Maria, Campus Santa Maria, Brazil. *E-mail address:* alejandro.ruiz-padillo@ufsm.br

^bTRYSE Research Group, University of Granada, ETSI Caminos, Canales y Puertos, Campus de Fuentenueva, s/n, 18071 Granada, Spain. *E-mail address:* jdona@ugr.es

Abstract

University cities record large numbers of daily trips to campuses, resulting in significant impacts on urban traffic. Public transport services are crucial for meeting this demand, especially for students, who form the most abundant group and are typically captive users of this mode. However, various factors including infrastructure, operation, safety, and environment influence the perception of public transport users regarding their daily trips. Therefore, this case study of a Brazilian university examines the relationships among these factors, using a structural equation modeling approach with multiple indicators and multiple causes (SEM-MIMIC), based on perception data from public transport users within the academic community. The results indicate the importance of incorporating safety perception into travel satisfaction models and considering the interaction between infrastructure and public transport operation attributes. It is also crucial to account for the attributes of the environment in which university students travel. Furthermore, the findings show that user perceptions are influenced by factors such as gender, vehicle availability, total travel time, and the adequacy of the service to cope with specific needs. Based on these findings, urban mobility and university managers can plan measures to effectively enhance the attractiveness of public transport and encourage its usage among members of the academic community.

1. Introduction

The main problems caused by current transport modes in cities, such as traffic jams, parking disputes, long travel times, pollution, and traffic accidents, stem from the excessive use of individual motorized vehicles and the lack of incentives and opportunities to adopt sustainable modes of transport, such as public transport, walking, and cycling (Hickman et al., 2013; Ko et al., 2019; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022). Moreover, there has been a decline in public transport usage for daily trips, which was further exacerbated by the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic (Oestreich et al., 2023). Therefore, it is necessary for public managers to make efforts to enhance the attractiveness of public transport (Fontoura et al., 2019; Guzman et al., 2020; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Soza-Parra et al., 2022).

Both public and private institutions that attract large numbers of people contribute to transport-related issues in urban systems (Balsas, 2003; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017). These organizations need to engage in travel management and plan actions that can improve the traffic situation in their vicinity (Guzman et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Zhan et al., 2016). In university cities, that is, urban centers with higher education institutions whose importance is key in the daily activity of the city, the trips made by members of the academic community to access campuses significantly contribute to traffic, resulting in considerable impacts on mobility in the area, especially before and after classes (Balsas, 2003; Zhan et al., 2016; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Limanond et al., 2011; Stein and Rodrigues da Silva, 2018). However, due to the unique characteristics of the academic community, particularly the student population, a specific study is required to understand the travel behavior related to university campuses (Hamad et al., 2021; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Nash and Mitra, 2019; Whalen et al. 2013; Zhan et al., 2016).

Universities are dynamic environments that foster diversity and the exchange of experiences, which can provide interesting contexts for implementing and validating sustainable mobility initiatives. Public transport is an essential transport mode for commuting to university campuses, since not all young people have access to personal motor vehicles, or may not even possess a driving license (Dewi et al., 2018; Gurrutxaga et al. al., 2017; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Zannat et al., 2020). Therefore, universities can serve as examples by providing students with sustainable transport options, contributing to societal change and awareness of the need to adopt sustainable practices (Balsas, 2003; Hamad et al., 2021; Limanond et al., 2011; Whalen et al., 2013; Zhan et al., 2016). Furthermore, students who regularly use public transport to access universities may become drivers in the future, so their earlier mobility behavior may be influential in determining their subsequent transport choices (Balsas, 2003; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010).

Numerous recent studies have sought to identify incentives and barriers to using public transport for commuting, including those focused on educational institutions, with the aim of promoting sustainable mobility (Hamad et al., 2021; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010 ; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Nash and Mitra, 2019; Soria-Lara et al., 2017; Stein and Rodrigues da Silva, 2018). To ensure appropriate public transport planning that aligns with the mobility needs of universities, it is crucial to consider the attributes that influence the choice of transport mode by the academic community (Dewi et al., 2018; Hamad et al., 2021; Whalen et al. 2013).

In this regard, the analysis of perceptions that contribute to the choice of transport mode and satisfaction among public transport users is particularly important (Allen et al., 2018; dell'Olio et al., 2010; De Oña, 2020; De Witte et al. al., 2013; Maia et al., 2020; Nash and Mitra, 2019; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Yilmaz and Ari, 2017). These attributes are related not only to the journey itself, but also to external environmental factors including pedestrian infrastructure between the home and the stops, as well as safety aspects (De Oña, 2020; Dewi et al., 2018; Rohani et al., 2013; Whalen et al. 2013).

In many developing countries, such as those in Latin America, rapid population growth, inadequate urban planning, increasing income levels, and high rates of motorization have negatively impacted the development of sustainable transport, particularly public transport, which often suffers from inadequate infrastructure and deficient operations (Allen et al., 2018; Fontoura et al., 2019; Guzman et al., 2020; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Maia et al., 2020; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Stein and Rodrigues da Silva, 2018; Tavares et al., 2021). Furthermore, these countries have witnessed expanded access to university education, leading to the construction of new campuses in smaller cities far from the capitals. However, there is a scarcity of studies specifically addressing this issue, concerning the university population (Hamad et al., 2021; Limanond et al., 2011; Nash and Mitra, 2019).

In this context, there is a research gap related to the travel behaviors of university community in small and medium sized cities in developing countries, especially regarding the aspects that influence the choice and satisfaction of public transport users. It is necessary to identify the relationships between the infrastructure and operational attributes of urban mobility, as well as with the specific aspects of the built environment and those related to safety, which may be different from those existing in large cities and for the population in general, or in developed countries. Likewise, the heterogeneity of the academic community members may influence their perceptions and the intensity of such relationships, making the generic planned actions to improve satisfaction in their trips to the university less effective.

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to analyze the relationships among different factors that contribute to choosing public transport for trips to the university, as well as subsequent satisfaction with its use, based on the perceptions of students and staff. The results aim to improve understanding of the interactions among infrastructure, operation, and environment, and their incorporation into models of transport mode selection and public transport satisfaction. The findings should assist relevant authorities in planning measures to promote the use of public transport within the academic community for daily trips to the university. In addition, such policies can be designed to meet the specific needs of these populations in the context of declining public transport use and scarce public resources. In this way, the results can help avoid replicating solutions designed for other scenarios that are inappropriate for these specific cases or maintaining ineffective strategies.

For this purpose, an analysis using Structural Equation Models (SEM) was applied, consisting of a measurement model using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to identify the relationships between the observed variables and the proposed latent factors, and structural regression models to verify the direct and indirect effects between the latent factors. Furthermore, a SEM-MIMIC (multiple indicators and multiple causes structural equation modeling) approach was used to verify the effects of the heterogeneity of the population analyzed on the results obtained.

In the remainder of this paper, Section 2 provides a literature review of the main aspects relevant to the objectives of the study. Section 3 presents the methodology employed, including a description of the study area, where a Latin American university is spread across multiple suburban campuses, the survey conducted to collect data, and the

analysis techniques employed. Section 4 discusses the main results obtained from application of the methodology, considering user perception data and the relevant literature, as well as practical applications for promoting public transport usage in the area analyzed. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main research conclusions and suggests possible future directions.

2. Literature review

There are various factors that influence the choice of transport mode and the satisfaction perceived of the trip. Aspects of the travel experience that can be highlighted are related to the geographical area in which the trip is taken and socioeconomic factors intrinsic to the user (Maia et al., 2020; De Witte et al., 2013; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Whalen et al., 2013). In the case of public transport, the specific characteristics of the mode have a great influence, from the perspectives of both the infrastructure and the operation of the system (Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Tavares et al., 2021; Zannat et al., 2020). Additional aspects that must be considered are related to the environments in which the different stages of the trip occur, including walking to stops, waiting for the service, and the journey itself in public vehicles (Dewi et al. al., 2018). Table 1 summarizes the relevant attributes identified in the literature.

Table 1. Attributes reported in the literature that influence the decision to use public transport and the satisfaction of users.

Aspects	Attributes (<i>variables</i>)	References
Public transport infrastructure (<i>Bus_infra</i>)	Public lighting at stops (<i>bus_stop_lighting</i>)	Berežný e Konečný, 2017; Dewi et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2021; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017
	Infrastructure of stops (canopies, benches...) (<i>bus_stop_infra</i>)	Allen et al., 2018; Berežný e Konečný, 2017; Dewi et al., 2018; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Li et al., 2022; Noor et al., 2014; Sakellariou et al., 2017; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017; Whalen et al. 2013
	Condition of the sidewalks on the way to and from the stop (<i>bus_stop_sidewalk</i>)	Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012; Zhan et al., 2016
	Total travel time including walking, waiting, and traveling (<i>bus_total_time</i>)	Allen et al., 2018; dell'Olio et al., 2010; De Witte et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Hamad et al., 2021; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Rohani et al., 2013; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Whalen et al. 2013; Zhan et al., 2016
	Exposure to noise and pollution in public transport (<i>bus_noise</i>)	Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017; Tavares et al., 2021; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Yilmaz and Ari, 2017
Public transport operation (<i>Bus_oper</i>)	Information about public transport lines and schedules (<i>bus_info</i>)	Berežný and Konečný, 2017; De Oña, 2020; De Witte et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022; Maia et al., 2020; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2021; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017

	Availability of schedules and public transport lines according to the needs of the user (<i>bus_availability</i>)	Allen et al., 2018; Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Fontoura et al., 2019; Dewi et al., 2018; De Witte et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Hamad et al., 2021; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Santoso et al., 2012; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017
	Punctuality and compliance with the planned frequency of public transport (<i>bus_punctuality</i>)	Allen et al., 2018; Berežný and Konečný, 2017; Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; dell’Olio et al., 2010; De Witte et al., 2013; Guzman et al., 2020; Hamad et al., 2021; Ko et al., 2019; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Tavares et al., 2021; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017
	Method of payment for the ticket in public transport (<i>bus_payment</i>)	De Witte et al., 2013; Li et al., 2022; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017
	Cost of the ticket (<i>bus_cost</i>)	Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; dell’Olio et al., 2010; De Witte et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Rohani et al., 2013; Soria-Lara et al., 2017; Tavares et al., 2021; Whalen et al., 2013; Zhan et al., 2016
	Comfort in public transport vehicles (<i>bus_comfort</i>)	Allen et al., 2018; dell’Olio et al., 2010; De Oña, 2020; Dewi et al., 2018; De Witte et al., 2013; Guzman et al., 2020; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Hamad et al., 2021; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2021; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017
Foot infrastructure (<i>Foot_infra</i>)	Ease of moving on sidewalks (<i>foot_ease</i>)	Orellana et al., 2020; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020
	State of conservation of the sidewalks (<i>sidewalk_infra</i>)	Orellana et al., 2020; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022
	Useful width of sidewalks (<i>sidewalk_width</i>)	Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020
	Public lighting (<i>public_lighting</i>)	Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020
	Trees and shade on the sidewalks (<i>foot_greenery</i>)	Orellana et al., 2020; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020
	Accessibility for people with reduced mobility (<i>foot_accessib</i>)	Orellana et al., 2020; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022
	Traffic signaling (vertical, horizontal...) (<i>traffic_signs</i>)	Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012
Safety (<i>Safety</i>)	Availability of pedestrian crossings (<i>crosswalk_avail</i>)	Orellana et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012; Zannat et al., 2020
	Gradients of the sidewalks (<i>sidewalk_grad</i>)	Orellana et al., 2020; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Zannat et al., 2020
	Safety related to traffic accidents in general (<i>geral_traffic_safety</i>)	dell’Olio et al., 2010; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012
	Safety related to robberies or thefts in general (<i>geral_public_safety</i>)	Balsas, 2003; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Maia et al., 2020; Noor et al., 2014; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012
	Safety related to traffic accidents in public	Allen et al., 2018; Cafiso et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Rohani et al., 2013; Tavares et al., 2021

	transport (<i>bus_traffic_safety</i>) Safety related to robberies or thefts in public transport (<i>bus_public_safety</i>)	Allen et al., 2018; dell'Olio et al., 2010; ; De Oña, 2020; Fontoura et al., 2019; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Maia et al., 2020; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Tavares et al., 2021; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017
Other environmental aspects (<i>Environment</i>)	Exposure to noise and pollution in general (<i>geral_noise</i>) Traffic congestion levels at peak hours (<i>geral_jam</i>) Vehicle speed in general (<i>geral_speed</i>) Need to control traffic (<i>geral_control</i>)	Fontoura et al., 2019; Tavares et al., 2021; Villaveces et al., 2012; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020 De Witte et al., 2013; Guzman et al., 2020; Maia et al., 2020; Tavares et al., 2021; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020 Stein and Rodrigues da Silva, 2018; Villaveces et al., 2012; Zannat et al., 2020 Guzman et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012

2.1 Public transport infrastructure characteristics.

In relation to infrastructure, the characteristics of public transport stops stand out, since they directly influence the experiences of passengers who board and leave collective vehicles. As they are the first element of the system with which the user comes into contact, such points must have an adequate design and sufficient capacity, providing a clean, illuminated, and accessible environment that can establish a satisfactory initial relationship between client and supplier (Dewi et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022; Noor et al., 2014; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017). In the specific case of the urban bus system, which is the most widely used service in developing countries, stopping points must also provide users with the basic elements of comfort, information, and protection (Allen et al., 2018; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017; Whalen et al. 2013). Furthermore, lighting at night increases the level of safety (Berežný and Konečný, 2017; Tavares et al., 2021).

Infrastructure aspects also include the conditions of the sidewalks along which users must walk from the start of the trip (usually the residence) to the stop, as well as the stop itself, since it constitutes an integral stage of the overall journey (Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012; Zhan et al., 2016). The characteristics of the infrastructure of the stops directly influence the modal choice and trip satisfaction, considering the times spent walking and waiting for the vehicle, which can be longer than the time spent in the public transport vehicle, consequently greatly increasing the total travel time (Allen et al., 2018; dell'Olio et al., 2010; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Rohani et al., 2013; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Whalen et al. 2013). In addition, if this time could be partially saved and used in another activity of interest to the user, it would lead to a more favorable attitude towards public transport systems that normally involve longer travel times and are therefore less attractive, compared to individual motorized modes (De Witte et al., 2013; Hamad et al., 2021; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Maia et al., 2020; Nash and Mitra, 2019; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Zhan et al., 2016; Whalen et al. 2013).

The conditions of the urban infrastructure related to the streets traveled by public transport vehicles also affect travel time. For urban buses, the existence of exclusive lanes and priority at intersections are important aspects, in addition to the maintenance conditions of the streets and vehicles (Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Maia et al., 2020; Soza-Parra et al., 2022). During journeys, these factors influence the exposure of users to noise and pollution generated by buses, as well as by traffic in general while waiting at stops (Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Tavares et al., 2021; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017). This is more evident in many cities in developing or underdeveloped countries, where the quality and conservation of street paving and vehicles may be quite precarious (Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Yilmaz and Ari, 2017).

2.2 Public transport operation aspects.

The other set of public transport characteristics that users consider when choosing their mode of transport is related to the operation of the system (Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; De Oña, 2020; Oestreich et al., 2023; Tavares et al., 2021). The cost is particularly relevant, since the more expensive it is to travel by public transport, relative to the option of driving a private vehicle, the more likely people are to use individual modes (dell'Olio et al., 2010; Berežný and Konečný, 2017; Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Maia et al., 2020; De Witte et al., 2013; Rohani et al., 2013). The impact of the cost of the ticket is usually greater for students, due to their lower economic capacity, but the usual discounts on fares for this group, together with the lack of their own vehicle, or even a driving license, encourage the use of public transport by young people (Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Santoso et al., 2012; Soria-Lara et al., 2017; Whalen et al. 2013; Zhan et al., 2016).

However, research on the improvement of public transport indicates that only a limited proportion of car drivers would use public transport if it was cheaper (De Witte et al., 2013; Guzman et al., 2020). Studies such as those by Whalen et al. (2013), Miralles-Guasch and Domene (2010) and Maia et al. (2020) indicate that the desire for comfort encourages the use of private vehicles. The overcrowding of users in collective vehicles is undesirable, while trips with passengers standing for considerable periods of time, heavy acceleration/deceleration, and/or excessive heat can result in the discomfort becoming unbearable (Allen et al., 2018; dell'Olio et al., 2010; De Oña, 2020; Hamad et al., 2021; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017). Related to this aspect is the method of paying for the ticket, which has a direct impact on user satisfaction, according to the time spent and the ease of accessing or recharging credits in the case of the increasingly common use of specific cards (De Witte et al., 2013; Li et al., 2022; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017).

Another decisive factor in choosing public transport is the availability of lines and schedules that enable the user to reach the destination at the right time (Allen et al., 2018; Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; De Oña, 2020; De Witte et al., 2013; Fontoura et al., 2019; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Santoso et al., 2012; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017). In the case of universities, the planning of the operation of the system must consider the need to include routes that cover the areas with the highest density of users

in the city, up to the accesses to the campus, as well as adequate services at times appropriate to the academic activities, especially during the periods of greatest student demand, which usually coincide with peak urban traffic flows (Dewi et al., 2018; Hamad et al., 2021; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017).

Therefore, a crucial issue is the reliability of the system (dell'Olio et al., 2010; Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Guzman et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; De Oña, 2020; Hamad et al., 2021; Noor et al., 2014; Santoso et al., 2012; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017), which is closely related to variations in the frequency of collective vehicles. If these variations are significant, they hinder adherence to schedules or frequencies, with uneven distribution of passengers between vehicles leading to saturation, especially at peak hours (De Witte et al., 2013; Ko et al., 2019). If the lack of punctuality is persistent, then customer confidence in the system may be compromised (Allen et al., 2018; Berežný and Konečný, 2017; Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Tavares et al., 2021). The existence of adequate information for users allows safer decision making (Berežný and Konečný, 2017; De Oña, 2020; De Witte et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Maia et al., 2020; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Tavares et al., 2021). New technologies, in addition to favoring intermodal integration and payments, contribute to improving the provision of information about schedules, lines, routes, and possible delays or incidents, facilitating it in real time and enhancing the user experience (Guzman et al., 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022; Oestreich et al., 2023; Soza-Parra et al., 2022; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017).

2.3 Walking infrastructure conditions.

All public transport users need to walk certain distances, generally from the home to the stop of origin, and from the point where they leave public transport to their destination, as well as for short trips in the environment, as occurs on university campuses (Zannat et al., 2020). Therefore, the aspects of urban infrastructure that affect mobility on foot must also be analyzed considering public transport users, since these aspects influence the ease of movement on the sidewalks and the final satisfaction with the trip (Guzman et al., 2020; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012; Zhan et al., 2016). This relationship may encourage or discourage greater use of public transport.

There are several attributes of the urban infrastructure that influence the satisfaction of pedestrians when they walk in the city (Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022). Satisfactory quality and state of conservation of the sidewalks are essential to facilitate movement on foot. In addition, the dimensioning of its useful width must ensure accessibility for all users, including those with reduced mobility (Orellana et al., 2020; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020). Likewise, the availability of safe and well-signposted pedestrian crossings on the way to and from the stops can significantly influence the decision to use public transport and the overall perception of travel (Villaveces et al., 2012; Zannat et al., 2020).

Other aspects of the urban environment that influence user satisfaction when walking are green spaces, which offer shade and shelter for pedestrians (Orellana et al., 2020;

Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020), and the gradient along the journey (Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Orellana et al., 2020; Zannat et al., 2020). In addition, the perception of the infrastructure related to walking is influenced by the presence and quality of public lighting and road signs (Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012).

2.4 Safety issues.

The use of public transport is usually greatly affected by public safety issues in the general context of the city, at stops, and within collective vehicles, since users may be more exposed to the risk of violence or robbery during their trips (Allen et al., 2018; dell'Olio et al., 2010; De Oña, 2020; Noor et al., 2014; Rohani et al., 2013; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017; Villaveces et al., 2012). General user satisfaction is affected by the perception of public and road safety in the environment, an aspect that has been highlighted as being of great importance in Latin America generally (Maia et al., 2020; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2021; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020), as well as in the surroundings of educational institutions (Balsas, 2003; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017). In the case of commuting by university students, Maia et al. (2020) indicate that higher crime rates in the environment or during trips reduce satisfaction with the use of public transport. Road accidents play an important role, since users may be exposed to the risks of traffic accidents in general and particularly within public transport. However, the normally low traffic accident rates of public transport vehicles, compared to others such as cars and motorcycles, act in their favor (Cafiso et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017).

2.5 Other urban environmental aspects.

Finally, the environment where the journey takes place also influences the perception and satisfaction of the user (Zannat et al., 2020; Nash and Mitra, 2019; Villaveces et al., 2012; Whalen et al. 2013). Among the various external environmental factors can be highlighted traffic jams, which generate higher costs and loss of time for the user of public transport, as well as noise and air pollution in the city (Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; De Witte et al., 2013; Fontoura et al., 2019; Guzman et al., 2020; Maia et al., 2020; Tavares et al., 2021; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012; Yilmaz and Ari, 2017). The speed of vehicles and official actions to ensure compliance with traffic regulations also influence satisfaction levels (Guzman et al., 2020; Stein and Rodrigues da Silva, 2018; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012).

2.6 Users' sociodemographic characteristics.

All factors identified do not affect the user in isolation or with the same importance, but are interrelated, with some being able to potentiate the effects of others, and vice versa (Ko et al., 2019; De Oña, 2020). Therefore, it is essential to study these relationships, as well as the effects of the perceptions of certain factors on the others and, consequently, on the satisfaction of public transport users. These perceptions will influence the choice of mode of transportation of the members of the university community, with consequent

impacts on the sustainability of public transportation systems and mobility in the city where the university is located.

Moreover, each user may have different perceptions of attributes described above, depending on their own personal characteristics (Allen et al., 2018; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; De Oña, 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Whalen et al. 2013; Zhan et al., 2016). Studies indicate that sociodemographic characteristics such as age, gender, and income level condition the transport behavior of users (De Witte et al., 2013; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Oestreich et al., 2023), including in the case of trips to university campuses (Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Hamad et al., 2021; Limanond et al., 2011; Maia et al., 2020; Soria-Lara et al., 2017; Nash and Mitra, 2019; Whalen et al., 2013). This has been observed in investigations in developing countries, such as those undertaken by Ko et al., (2019), Hamad et al. (2021), Harbering and Schlüter (2020) and Maia et al. (2020), which found that women are more likely than men to use public transport. On the other hand, people with higher incomes are more likely to use the car, while those with lower incomes have a greater probability of choosing public transport (Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; De Witte et al., 2013; Guzman et al., 2020; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Hamad et al., 2021; Oestreich et al., 2023). This behavior has been reported for trips to school or university, as in the studies by Nash and Mitra (2019) and Maia et al. (2020).

When people own motorized vehicles, the use of public transport modes decreases, while those without access to a motorcycle or a car are dependent on public transport when they need to travel long distances (Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Limanond et al., 2011; Maia et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; De Witte et al., 2013; Oestreich et al., 2023). It is important to consider that not all young people have a motorized vehicle available for their own use, while vehicle ownership can affect the perception of students regarding public transport (Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Hamad et al. al., 2021; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010). Maia et al. (2020) point out that one of the reasons that university students may consider car ownership to be desirable, to the detriment of public transport, is that the private vehicle offers higher levels of safety and autonomy.

Travel time is an important factor in the choice of transport mode, especially for trips by public transport that may involve longer distances, and can be valued differently according to each person (Guzman et al., 2020; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Soria-Lara et al., 2017; Santoso et al., 2012; Whalen et al. 2013). The total time required is influenced by the location of the residence and the destination, since the proximity of the public transport stops determines the distance to walk, while the perception of the total time spent in traveling can vary (Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Hamad et al., 2021; Ko et al., 2019; Noor et al., 2014). The need to make a transfer during the journey also has an influence, because changing the public transport mode or line can lead to a different perception of the entire trip (Noor et al., 2014; Santoso et al. al., 2012; Soria-Lara et al., 2017; Whalen et al. 2013). Transfers may constitute a travel penalty, due to the additional wait that may occur during the change, or to excessive walking between transfer points (Allen et al., 2018; De Witte et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Guzman et al., 2020; Miralles-Guasch and Domene, 2010; Soza-Parra et al., 2022). This aspect may also be relevant when undertaking a

single trip for multiple activities, instead of making separate trips for different activities (such as shopping, sports, or taking the children to school), in relation to the main trip (Bhat and Sardesai, 2006; De Witte et al., 2013; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020).

3. Methodology

3.1 Case study

The study was conducted in the four cities where the Federal University of Santa Maria (UFSM) has campuses, with administrative buildings, classrooms, teacher offices, laboratories, libraries, student housing and other services such as restaurants. The university facilities are located in the suburban areas of the cities of Santa Maria (headquarters campus), Cachoeira do Sul, Palmeira das Missões, and Frederico Westphalen, in the interior of the state of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil (Figure 1). Santa Maria is a medium sized city, with an estimated population of 285,159 inhabitants in 2021, while the other three locations are smaller cities (81,869, 32,967, and 31,675 inhabitants, respectively) (IBGE, 2021). The use of individual motor vehicles in the state is very high, as shown by the rate data of 48 vehicles per 100 inhabitants and the fact that around 55% of the population possesses a driving license. In fact, almost 50% of the population usually travels by car to their main activity, and only 20% uses public transport (IBGE, 2021; Oestreich et al., 2023). Table A1 (in Appendix A) presents some of the main demographic data of the four cities in the study scenario.

During the research period, the academic community consisted of 25,846 people, including students, teachers, and administrative staff (UFSM, 2021). Table A2 (in Appendix A) details the sociodemographic distribution of the academic community. In all cases, the role of public transport is essential due to the location of the campuses and because all staff members and the vast majority of students live off campus, usually in central areas of cities. The only mode of public transport is the urban bus, which has specific lines to the UFSM campuses.

Figure 1. Locations of cities with Federal University of Santa Maria campuses.

3.2. Survey

The research survey was applied online and anonymously in February 2021 through the institution’s internal system. Thus, all students, teachers and administrative staff were invited to answer a research instrument, including questions related to personal data, mode of transportation used to get to the university, and perception of the attributes identified in the literature review in relation to public transport, as well as concerning pedestrian infrastructure and mobility in general (see Table 1), when traveling to the different campuses. The responses to the perception questions were given using a five-point scale: “very bad” (1), “bad” (2), “regular” (3), “good” (4), and “very good” (5). Many works analyzing perceptions or quality evaluations using ordinal scales have shown that the application of SEM to these data is appropriate (Allen et al., 2018; Kline, 2015; De Oña, 2020; Li et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2021; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020). Thus, the questionnaire included questions such as “Considering your trips to the university, evaluate the lighting at public transport stops at night” (in the case of the *bus_stop_lighting* variable, for example).

From all the responses obtained in the survey, the sample corresponding to those academic community members who indicated public transport as their usual mode of travel to the university was extracted, with a total of 1,657 frequent bus users commuting to the campuses. The sample was representative of the population, in terms of destination campus, gender, and relationship with the institution (students, teachers, and administrative staff). It should be noted that the proportion of public transport users among the academic population, close to 40%, was typical of university campuses located in suburban areas (Berežný and Konečný, 2017; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020;

Limanond et al., 2011; Miralles -Guasch and Domene, 2010; Stein and Rodrigues da Silva, 2018).

3.3. SEM-MIMIC

Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to identify the relationships and effects among the attributes analyzed based on the perceptions of the members of the university community concerning their regular trips to the campus. Modeling of the relationships used the covariances and the means of the observed variables (representing the investigated attributes), applying multivariate statistical techniques composed of a structural regression model to measure the direction and strength of the relationships among the unobserved latent variables (which configure the constructs), as well as a measurement model of the latent variables with linear functions of observed variables (Allen et al., 2018; Kline, 2015; De Oña, 2020; Li et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2021; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020; Yilmaz and Ari, 2017). The use of SEM assumes homoscedasticity of the data, with the observed errors being normally distributed and presenting uniform variances at all levels of the dependent variables, while the variables not included in the regression are not correlated with the observed variables.

Firstly, the structural model is specified, with the latent constructs and the relationships with the observed variables being represented in diagrams and analyzed using a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) measurement model, in order to test different models and generate the most appropriate model for the problem studied. The model identified should provide a unique set of parameter estimates. In a second step, the proposed structural model is tested and adjusted, based on the specified measurement model. The regression coefficients are estimated by the maximum likelihood (ML) method, representing the direct effects of the latent variables on the observed variables. For each model, the quality of the fit to the data is evaluated and the consistency of the results is analyzed according to the problem studied. Among the valid models, the one with the best statistical fit parameters and the most coherent interpretation of the study scenario is chosen.

Finally, the analysis was completed using a SEM-MIMIC (multiple indicators and multiple causes structural equation modeling) approach that allowed testing of the effects of socioeconomic characteristics and travel routines on the constructs considered, as well as comparison of subgroups within the sample (De Oña, 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Allen et al., 2018; Santoso et al., 2012).

All the statistical analyses were performed using Stata/MP 16.1. Prior to the application of SEM, the necessary homoscedasticity and covariance checks were made, together with normality checks. Application of the Shapiro-Wilk test showed that the variables were not normally distributed, which was due to the origin of the data. Therefore, correction was performed using the Satorra-Bentler method for the chi-square test and adjustment of the model (Kline, 2015; De Oña, 2020; Yilmaz and Ari, 2017).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Statistical description of data

Firstly, the data from the responses to the survey were statistically evaluated to characterize the selected sample. Table 2 summarizes the socioeconomic characteristics and those related to mobility profiles for travel to the University campuses.

Table 2: Socioeconomic and mobility characteristics of the sample (n=1,657)

Characteristic	Group	Proportion
Gender	Male	35.49%
	Female	64.51%
Age (years)	16-29	68.92%
	30-49	24.98%
	50-64	5.43%
	65 or more	0.66%
Type	Student	92.07%
	Administration staff	4.71%
	Teacher	2.60%
Campus	Santa Maria	87.45%
	Cachoeira do Sul	3.80%
	Frederico Westphalen	5.07%
	Palmeira das Missões	3.68%
Household net income (number of minimum wages)	< 2	35.97%
	2-4	32.59%
	> 4	24.32%
	Not informed	7.12%
Possession of driving license	Yes	51.72%
	No	48.28%
Availability of motor vehicle	Yes	35.19%
	No	64.81%
Distance of bus stop to residence (number of blocks)	< 4	47.80%
	4 or more	52.20%
Journey time (min)	< 30	43.69%
	30 or more	56.31%
Frequency of commuting (days/week)	0-2	5.07%
	3-4	13.10%
	5 or more	81.83%
Carrying out secondary activities on the journey to/from campus	Yes	39.05%
	No	60.95%
Need of bus transfer	Yes	32.59%
	No	61.41%

The representativeness of the sample was confirmed in terms of sociodemographic stratification of the study scenario and the distribution of the academic community when compared with the data presented in Table A2 (in Appendix A). Therefore, the 1,657 members of the academic community surveyed who used the bus for their regular trips to the University were mostly young, female students, in proportions representative of the university population at the four campuses. The distribution of the survey participants according to income range was also consistent with the salary range of the study population, with the members with the lowest income corresponding to a part of the students. Approximately half of the individuals possessed a driving license. However, while almost all the university workers had a license, far fewer students, especially the youngest, had obtained one.

Although all the respondents were habitual bus users, a third of them indicated that they had a motor vehicle (car or motorcycle) available. Most of them reported a bus stop near their residence and took more than 30 minutes to reach their destination, highlighting the distance of the campuses from the urban centers of the cities. A large proportion of the respondents commuted to the university 5 or more days a week, without the need to transfer and without making intermediate stops for other secondary activities.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of responses, mean values and standard deviations for the attributes included in the different constructs proposed based on the literature review (Table 1).

Different evaluations of the attributes by the academic community are identified. The attributes related to the infrastructure for walking (*Foot_infra*) were generally perceived in a better way, highlighting the ease of walking on the sidewalks (3.84), but the perception of the quality of this infrastructure in the area of the stop (*bus_stop_sidewalk*) had poorer evaluation (2.66), as did the other attributes of the infrastructure related to the bus trip. The other attributes of the public transport infrastructure also received low ratings, especially those related to stops.

Another notable difference was in relation to the perception of safety in general (*geral_traffic_safety*), compared to that perceived inside buses, which was much worse for both traffic accidents (*bus_traffic_safety*) and thefts (*bus_public_safety*). Attributes such as accessibility for people with reduced mobility had lower evaluation (*foot_accessib*: 3.21), highlighting the lack of adaptation of many of the sidewalks and pedestrian crossings for this population, including within the campus. This is a common pattern in cities of Latin American countries (Orellana et al., 2020). Among the environmental attributes, the participants in the study expressed an adequate perception in relation to exposure to noise and pollution on campus (*geral_noise*: 3.33), although a much worse rating was given for the environment inside the bus (*bus_noise*: 2.44), probably due to the paving conditions of many streets along the routes, as well as the age and poor condition of many of the buses. It is also interesting to highlight the worse perception of the respondents regarding the levels of congestion at peak hours (*geral_jam*: 2.80), reflecting the problem of excessive use of cars to access the university, especially the headquarters campus.

Figure 2: Descriptive statistics of the indicators of the sample of responses to the survey.

Among the attributes that received the worst ratings on average were those related to public transport operation, especially the cost of the ticket (*bus_cost*: 2.19) and comfort (*bus_comfort*: 2.32). These results evidenced negative perceptions of the users, largely due to overcrowding in buses at peak times, the lack of air conditioning, and the general condition of the vehicles. The specific attributes concerning availability (*bus_availability*: 2.72) and information about lines and schedules (*bus_info*: 2.84), which were quite limited, stood out among the attributes that received the worst ratings by bus users.

4.2. SEM results

The SEM methodology described in subsection 3.3 was applied to the data obtained from the survey on users' perceptions of mobility attributes, which were used as observed variables of the proposed constructs. The results of the measurement model and the stages of fitting the SEM models are detailed in Appendices B and C, respectively.

As shown in Figure 3, the final structural regression model tested included direct influences of the latent variables *Foot_infra*, *Bus_infra* and *Safety* on the *Environment* construct (Dewi et al., 2018). In addition, *Bus_oper* influenced *Bus_infra*, which was also related to *Environment* by means of the mediation of *Safety*. Finally, the *Safety* construct also influenced the perception of the attributes related to pedestrian mobility (*Foot_infra*) (Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022).

Figure 3. Final model.

Table 3 shows the results of the final structural regression model. The approximated fit indices of the model were acceptable (CFI and TLI greater than 0.85, and SRMR and RMSEA lower than 0.08). In addition, the ability to explain the variation in the

perception of endogenous latent variables (R^2) was satisfactory, with values greater than 0.80.

Table 3. Structural paths and model's fit statistics for final structural regression model

MODEL / Path	Unst.	SE	St.
<i>Safety -> Foot_infra</i>	0.800	0.050	0.735
<i>Foot_infra -> Environment</i>	0.193	0.041	0.184
<i>Bus_infra -> Environment</i>	0.175	0.024	0.196
<i>Safety -> Environment</i>	0.637	0.062	0.556
<i>Bus_oper -> Bus_infra</i>	0.892	0.036	0.912
<i>Bus_infra -> Safety</i>	0.467	0.029	0.599
Model's fit statistics (Satorra-Bentler estimation)			
df (sb)		340	
chi-square (sb)		2457.88	
p-value		0.000	
RMSEA (sb)		0.061	
CFI (sb)		0.884	
TLI (sb)		0.871	
SRMR		0.070	
AIC		109303.146	
BIC		109811.945	
R^2 <i>Foot_infra</i>		0.846	
R^2 <i>Environment</i>		0.887	
R^2 <i>Bus_infra</i>		0.921	
R^2 <i>Safety</i>		0.818	

All unstandardized estimates are statistically significant at $p < 0.001$

4.3. SEM-MICIC results

Analysis of the influence of socioeconomic variables and transport routines in the estimation of the attributes studied in the structural model was carried out using the SEM-MIMIC technique. For this, the influences of the following characteristics on the five latent variables were considered:

- Gender: the dummy *male* variable was used, taking the female gender as a reference.
- Monthly family income: taking the three income categories obtained with information from the respondents, defined in Table 2, two dummy variables were created, using the lowest level as a reference (< 2 minimum wages): *inc_med* (2-4 minimum wages) and *inc_high* (> 4 minimum wages). Removal of the cases where the family income was not informed reduced the sample to $n = 1,539$.
- Availability of a motorized vehicle in the residence: people with or without (reference) a car or motorcycle available: *motor_available*.

- Travel time to the university: the variable *time_high* was used, taking as a reference those members of the academic community who took less than 30 minutes for their usual commute.
- Carrying out secondary activities during the trip to the university, considered by the *activities* variable, where the reference was those who did not carry out any secondary activity.
- Distance from the residence to a bus stop: the variable *bus_stop_far* was used, taking as a reference those who needed to travel less than 4 blocks (approximately 500 m, as indicated by Zhan et al. (2016)) to reach a bus stop.
- Requirement for public transport transfers when traveling to the University: users who did not need to transfer were considered as a reference in the variable *transfer_bus*.

Figure 4 shows the proposed SEM-MIMIC model. Table 4 shows the unstandardized and standardized values of the influence results between the latent variables (structural paths) and of the regressors that were statistically significant. As can be seen, all the regressors were significant in at least one construct. The results for the model fit parameters were acceptable, with improvements of RMSEA and SRMR, compared to the original model, although the CFI and TLI values were slightly worse (but still >0.85). In general, the estimates of the parameters in the structural paths of the model presented very slight variation, compared to the original model, indicating that the heterogeneity of the sample was not high.

Figure 4. SEM-MIMIC model

Table 4. SEM-MIMIC results: structural paths, statistically significant regressors' influence and selected fit statistics

Path / Regressor / Fit index	Unst.	SE	Std.
<i>Safety</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>	0.781	0.051	0.718

<i>Foot_infra -> Environment</i>	0.196	0.041	0.185
<i>Bus_infra -> Environment</i>	0.182	0.025	0.204
<i>Safety -> Environment</i>	0.642	0.063	0.557
<i>Bus_oper -> Bus_infra</i>	0.792	0.031	0.886
<i>Bus_infra -> Safety</i>	0.465	0.03	0.601
		<i>Bus_infra</i>	
<i>male</i>	0.087	0.026	0.062
<i>time_high</i>	-0.106	0.027	-0.078
<i>bus_stop_far</i>	-0.122	0.025	-0.09
<i>transfer_bus</i>	-0.101	0.028	-0.07
		<i>Environment</i>	
<i>male</i>	-0.051	0.025	-0.04
<i>inc_med</i>	-0.064	0.026	-0.051
<i>inc_high</i>	<u>-0.090</u>	0.028	-0.066
<i>bus_stop_far</i>	0.048	0.023	0.04
		<i>Bus_oper</i>	
<i>inc_high</i>	0.106	0.042	0.062
<i>motor_available</i>	0.219	0.038	0.139
<i>time_high</i>	<u>-0.112</u>	0.04	-0.073
<i>activities</i>	-0.236	0.037	-0.152
<i>transfer_bus</i>	-0.182	0.041	-0.113
		<i>Safety</i>	
<i>male</i>	0.176	0.025	0.161
<i>time_high</i>	0.085	0.024	0.08

Model's fit statistics (Satorra-Bentler estimation)

df (sb)	549
chi-square (sb)	2864.22
p-value	0.000
RMSEA (sb)	0.052
CFI (sb)	0.877
TLI (sb)	0.865
SRMR	0.059
AIC	117621.302
BIC	118438.152
R ² <i>Foot_infra</i>	0.843
R ² <i>Environment</i>	0.886
R ² <i>Bus_infra</i>	0.931
R ² <i>Bus_oper</i>	0.471
R ² <i>Safety</i>	0.832

All unstandardized values are statistically significant at $p < 0.001$, except underlined values (statistically significant at $p < 0.01$) and in *italics* (statistically significant at $p < 0.05$).

The following conclusions could be drawn from the analysis of the results of the model (Figure 4):

- There is a strong influence of the perception of safety aspects when the user is moving on foot between the bus stops and the origin and destination. A sense of safety (*Safety*) positively affected the perception of urban infrastructure for walking (*Foot_infra*). This finding is consistent with the literature, particularly in the Latin American context, where attributes such as safety against robbery, violence, and traffic accidents are considered crucial for walkability and the attractiveness of the urban environment (Maia et al., 2020; Ruiz-Padillo et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2021; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020). Therefore, the positive perception of infrastructure attributes for walking on the campus (Figure 4) may be influenced by the general sense of safety among members of the academic community.

- The perception of safety (*Safety*), both in general (*geral_traffic_safety* and *geral_public_safety*) and inside buses (*bus_traffic_safety* and *bus_public_safety*), directly impacts users' perceptions of their surroundings (*Environment*), including the operation of traffic (such as traffic jams – *geral_jam*), vehicle speed (*geral_speed*), and compliance with traffic safety regulations (*geral_control*). This relationship has been identified in previous studies, particularly in the Latin American context (Guzman et al., 2020; Villaveces et al., 2012), and was also evident in the present case study, with a regular perception rating. These results highlight the importance of public authorities prioritizing safety conditions in cities, especially in the vicinity of university campuses, in order to improve users' perceptions of sustainable mobility aspects and encourage its adoption for commuting to the university.

- The relationship between safety (*Safety*) and the environment is indirectly reinforced by the influence of the perception of the infrastructure for walking (*Foot_infra*) on the *Environment*. Users recognize that deficiencies in pedestrian-friendly infrastructure negatively affect their perception of externalities caused by unsustainable traffic patterns (Dewi et al., 2018; Hickman et al., 2013; Ko et al., 2019; Guzman et al., 2020). In other words, when bus users perceive inadequate urban infrastructure for pedestrians, as was the case in the surroundings of the campuses studied here, they conclude that the traffic environment is unfriendly, leading to consequences such as pollution, noise (*geral_noise*), and traffic congestion (*geral_jam*). Therefore, providing the university community with perceived safe and pleasant walking environments helps to cultivate a more sustainable and respectful awareness regarding traffic, which can influence other daily activities and extend beyond the time spent at the institution.

- Users' perceptions of bus infrastructure (*Bus_infra*) directly and indirectly (through *Safety*) influence their perceptions of the *Environment*. On one hand, users' perceptions of attributes such as lighting (*bus_stop_lighting*), bus stop infrastructure (*bus_stop_infra*), and their experience during walking to and from bus stops (*bus_stop_sidewalk*) affect their sense of safety in movement, encompassing public safety (*bus_public_safety* and *geral_public_safety*) (Berežný and Konečný, 2017; Tavares et al., 2021) and traffic safety (*bus_traffic_safety* and *geral_traffic_safety*) (Cafiso et al., 2013; Noor et al., 2014). Notably, the sample population analyzed gave relatively low average ratings regarding these attributes (Figure 2). On the other hand, users' perceptions of these infrastructure attributes (*Bus_infra*) also influence their perceptions of traffic externalities (*Environment*) (Guzman et al., 2020; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020), albeit to a lesser extent. There is also an

indirect influence between perceptions of public transport infrastructure (*Bus_infra*) and *Environment*, mediated by *Safety* and infrastructure for walking (*Foot_infra*). This reinforces the need to provide adequate conditions for sidewalks, bus stops, and public lighting, in order to enhance user satisfaction at all stages of the journey to the campus.

- The results also demonstrate a direct relationship between the users' perception of public transport operation (*Bus_oper*) and their perception of infrastructure characteristics (*Bus_infra*), which, in turn, impact other constructs in the model (*Safety* and *Environment*), as previously highlighted in the studies with university populations by Maia et al. (2020) and Whalen et al. (2013). This direct influence highlights the importance of improving operation aspects such as *bus_availability*, *bus_info*, *bus_punctuality*, and *bus_comfort* (which received generally negative evaluations), in order to enhance user satisfaction regarding travel time (*bus_total_time*) and reduce exposure to noise and pollution during the trip, both inside the bus and while waiting at the bus stop (*bus_noise* and *geral_noise*).

- Lastly, it is worth noting that there is no direct influence between constructs related to infrastructure for walking (*Foot_infra*) and those related to public transport operation (*Bus_oper*). This finding is logical, since the infrastructure attributes assessed by users pertain to different parts of the overall trip to the campus. However, the perception of all these factors collectively influences the overall trip satisfaction and perception of the environment. Therefore, they are interdependent and synergistic factors for improving the users' experience of public transport modes (Zhan et al., 2020).

Moreover, the results of the SEM-MIMIC model indicated that being a man (*male*) improves the perception of public transport infrastructure (*Bus_infra*) and *Safety*, while it reduces the perception of the *Environment*. These results are consistent with previous studies (De Oña, 2020), particularly considering the greater use of public transport by the women in the sample (Hamad et al., 2021; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Ko et al., 2019; Maia et al., 2020; Oestreich et al., 2023; Zhan et al., 2016) and the greater risks faced in their habitual trips, especially in the Latin American context, where the study was undertaken (Allen et al., 2018; Harbering and Schlüter, 2020; Ruiz -Padillo et al., 2022). Likewise, the perception of environmental aspects is worse for users with higher levels of family income (*inc_med* or *inc_high*) and who do not need to walk far to the stop (*bus_stop_far*), which reflects a negative perception of the environment related to traffic and pollution problems.

On the other hand, users who have a private vehicle (*motor_available*) and higher income (*inc_high*) have a better perception in relation to the operation of public transport (*Bus_oper*) (although less significant), probably because they are users of public transport "by choice", since they would have the possibility of traveling individually to the campus (they are non-captive users of public transport). It is likely that if the schedules and lines meet the needs of these users and the impact of the cost on their income is lower, their satisfaction with the service rises, as observed by De Oña (2020). This effect is greater in the case of students, who benefit from a discount on the bus fare (Nash and Mitra, 2019; Maia et al., 2020). In addition, when the time spent in commuting is not high, these users do not appear to be as dependent on the car (Ko et al., 2019). However, the fact of spending a lot of time traveling (*time_high*) and the

need for intermediate stops to transfer (*transfer_bus*) generate a worse perception of the infrastructure attributes (*Bus_infra*) and operation of public transport (*Bus_oper*), probably because they do not adequately address their interests (Santoso et al., 2012). Likewise, a negative influence on the perception of the public transport infrastructure (*Bus_infra*) is detected if the bus stop is far from the residence (*bus_stop_far*), for the same reasons as above (Zhan et al., 2016). The *activities* regressor also has a negative effect on *Bus_oper*, indicating that carrying out other activities during the main trip to the university worsens the perception of public transport operation (De Oña, 2020; De Witte et al., 2013).

These results highlight the need to increase efforts to improve the perception of safety for the female population, and promote pleasant and attractive environments in cities, especially around educational centers and other trip attractors, to encourage the use of sustainable modes of transport. In addition, the findings emphasize the importance improving the quality of public transport modes, both from the point of view of the infrastructure of the stops and the operation of the system, while maintaining a price appropriate to the needs of the users.

Table 5 presents the values of the direct, indirect, and total effects among the latent variables for each structural path, as well as the regressors analyzed in the SEM-MIMIC model. In relation to structural paths, for which the non-standardized values were all significant, the values of the effects greater than 0.50, which are considered high (Allen et al., 2018), can be highlighted: the direct effect of the public transport operation (*Bus_oper*) on its infrastructure (*Bus_infra*) (0.792), as well as *Safety* on infrastructure for walking (*Foot_infra*) (0.781), and *Safety* on the *Environment* (0.642), which, added to the indirect effect mediated by *Foot_infra*, increased the total effect to a value of 0.795. On the other hand, the direct effect of the public transport infrastructure (*Bus_infra*) on the *Environment* was the smallest, but when the indirect effect mediated by *Safety* was added, its value increased to 0.552. The indirect effect values were only moderate (between 0.30 and 0.50) or low (<0.30), highlighting the indirect effect of the public transport operation (*Bus_oper*) on the *Environment* (0.437), as already identified in the SEM model.

Table 5. SEM-MIMIC results: direct, indirect and total effects

Structural paths	Direct	Indirect	T. effect
<i>Safety</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>	0.781		0.781
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		0.363	0.363
<i>Bus_oper</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		0.288	0.288
<i>Bus_oper</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>	0.792		0.792
<i>Foot_infra</i> -> <i>Environment</i>	0.196		0.196
<i>Safety</i> -> <i>Environment</i>	0.642	0.153	0.795
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>Environment</i>	0.182	0.370	0.552
<i>Bus_oper</i> -> <i>Environment</i>		0.437	0.437
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>Safety</i>	0.465		0.465
<i>Bus_oper</i> -> <i>Safety</i>		0.368	0.368
Regressors' influence			

<i>male</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		0.169	0.169
<i>male</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>	<u>0.087</u>		<u>0.087</u>
<i>male</i> -> <i>Environment</i>	-0.051	0.188	0.137
<i>male</i> -> <i>Safety</i>	0.176	<u>0.041</u>	0.216
<i>motor_available</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		0.063	0.063
<i>motor_available</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>		0.173	0.173
<i>motor_available</i> -> <i>Environment</i>		0.096	0.096
<i>motor_available</i> -> <i>Safety</i>		0.081	0.081
<i>motor_available</i> -> <i>Bus_oper</i>	0.219		0.219
<i>inc_high</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		<i>0.031</i>	<i>0.031</i>
<i>inc_high</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>		<i>0.084</i>	<i>0.084</i>
<i>inc_high</i> -> <i>Safety</i>		<i>0.039</i>	<i>0.039</i>
<i>inc_high</i> -> <i>Bus_oper</i>	<i>0.106</i>		<i>0.106</i>
<i>inc_med</i> -> <i>Environment</i>	-0.064		-0.064
<i>transfer_bus</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		-0.089	-0.089
<i>transfer_bus</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>	-0.101	-0.144	-0.245
<i>transfer_bus</i> -> <i>Environment</i>		-0.136	-0.136
<i>transfer_bus</i> -> <i>Safety</i>		-0.114	-0.114
<i>transfer_bus</i> -> <i>Bus_oper</i>	-0.182		-0.182
<i>activities</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		-0.068	-0.068
<i>activities</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>		-0.187	-0.187
<i>activities</i> -> <i>Environment</i>		-0.103	-0.103
<i>activities</i> -> <i>Safety</i>		-0.087	-0.087
<i>activities</i> -> <i>Bus_oper</i>	-0.236		-0.236
<i>time_high</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>	-0.106	<u>-0.088</u>	-0.195
<i>time_high</i> -> <i>Bus_oper</i>	<u>-0.112</u>		<u>-0.112</u>
<i>bus_stop_far</i> -> <i>Foot_infra</i>		-0.044	-0.044
<i>bus_stop_far</i> -> <i>Bus_infra</i>	-0.122		-0.122
<i>bus_stop_far</i> -> <i>Safety</i>		-0.057	-0.057

All unstandardized values are statistically significant at $p < 0.001$, except underlined values (statistically significant at $p < 0.01$) and in *italics* (statistically significant at $p < 0.05$).

Among the significant effects of the regressors, the total positive effects that the *male* variable presents on the *Environment*, *Foot_infra*, and *Safety* constructs stand out, indicating that being a man improves perceptions of these aspects. In a context in which there is a significant female population, such as the university (Table 2), this result highlights the need for the responsible authorities to improve these aspects and enhance the satisfaction of a greater proportion of the academic community, to encourage them to use public transport.

The total effects that owning individual motor vehicles (*motor_available*) have on the constructs related to public transport (*Bus_infra* and *Bus_oper*) are also important, reinforcing the notion that non-captive users have a better perception of public transport, compared to captive users (Miralles-Guasch and Domine, 2010). Analogous results, although with a lower effect, were found in relation to members of the academic community with higher incomes (*inc_high* on *Bus_infra* and *Bus_oper*). These results

suggest that investments in improving the infrastructure and operating conditions of public transport could have a beneficial effect in maintaining the loyalty of its users, even when they have economic conditions to switch to the individual motorized mode, as well as in attracting new users. In addition, in the case of young university populations, these experiences may favor the continuation of more sustainable practices during their later working lives.

Finally, the need to make transfers (*transfer_bus*) or carry out secondary activities (*activities*) during the trip, as well as long travel times (*time_high*) and not having a bus stop close to the residence (*bus_stop_far*), have significant negative effects on the final perception results of these users, especially in the *Bus_oper* and *Bus_infra* constructs (Ko et al., 2019). Among these effects, the case of two regressors stands out: *activities*, indicating that the characteristics of public transport do not meet the needs of these users; and *transfer_bus*, highlighting the fact that needing to transfer to arrive at the University significantly worsens the final satisfaction of the trip (De Witte et al., 2013; Santoso et al., 2012). Therefore, coordination between university managers and the authorities responsible for planning and operating the transportation system is essential for organizing the bus lines and schedules for transport to the campuses, to better serve the academic population. In the context of developing countries, this relationship implies the need to formulate public policies for accessible housing for students, especially low-income students (who are the majority in public institutions), in areas closest to the public transportation routes to campus.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

The challenges faced by cities today, regarding the negative impacts of excessive use of individual motorized transportation, necessitate proper planning of public transport services that encourage their use by the population. In university cities, the mobility patterns of the academic community exhibit specific characteristics and contribute significantly to urban traffic, particularly with respect to the utilization of public transport. Hence, the aim of this study was to analyze the interactions among attributes that influence the perception of public transport by the university community. To achieve this, structural equation models were employed, based on the perceptions of attributes related to public transport infrastructure and operations, pedestrian infrastructure, safety aspects, and the urban environment, gathered from a sample of students, teachers, and administrative staff at a multi-campus university located in small and medium sized cities in southern Brazil.

The results indicated a direct influence of safety aspects on the perception of users when walking between public transport stops and their origin/destination, as well as on their perception of the surrounding environment. Furthermore, there was a direct influence of the users' perception of public transport infrastructure on their perception of urban environment aspects, mediated by their perception of safety. Additionally, the perceptions of public transport operation attributes significantly influenced the users' perception of infrastructure characteristics and, consequently, other constructs within the model. These results highlight the importance of providing adequate conditions for sidewalks, bus stops, public lighting, and the built environment in general, to improve

user satisfaction and perceptions of safety when traveling to campus. On the other hand, with regard to the quality of public transport, the results identified the greatest influence of aspects such as availability, information, reliability, and the condition of the vehicles. It is important to emphasize that such improvements in walking and public transport infrastructure contribute to improving the perception and satisfaction of the general population of the city, not just the academic community.

Analysis of the influence of the users' socioeconomic characteristics on these attributes revealed notable differences between men and women, reflecting the greater risks faced by women, especially young university students, while using public transport. Effects related to income level and access to private motorized vehicles were also noted, as well as the impact of long walks to stops or transfers during the journey. Therefore, adequate planning of the public transport system and improvements to the characteristics of the urban built environment are crucial to encouraging the adoption and maintenance of the use of sustainable transport modes.

These findings emphasize the need for collaboration between public and private managers responsible for universities and urban mobility, in order to improve the infrastructure conditions of public transport stops, as well as to enhance pedestrian accessibility. The results highlight the importance of planning public transport routes and schedules to effectively serve the university population, focusing on factors such as availability, reliability, information, comfort, and ensuring the highest possible level of safety throughout the entire journey. However, the larger proportion of students in the sample analyzed may condition a specific relationship of the results obtained with this profile of the academic community. Therefore, the proposed improvements may be less attractive and efficient for teachers and other staff members since they present different characteristics to students.

In conclusion, conducting studies like this one, in the context of developing countries, is crucial for improving understanding of the relationships among public transport attributes and user satisfaction models, which have primarily considered case studies in larger Western cities. The focus on the university population and the analysis of the influence of its heterogeneity on attribute perceptions represents a unique contribution, compared to previous research. The results obtained can assist in the proposal of measures to promote public transport usage and to foster long-term sustainable mobility practices. However, the constant changes in transportation technologies and education models worldwide may require adjustments to the conclusions obtained from this study, as these aspects were not considered in the models.

Therefore, further research is recommended to fully understand the choices of transport mode among university staff and students, as well as the influence of the geographical proximity between homes and campuses on perceptions of the different urban mobility attributes. Additionally, an analysis over time of the perceived effects of applying mobility plans or changes in travel patterns in university cities may be necessary. Finally, it would also be beneficial to compare the results of this study with those obtained for other trip generation hubs, such as major administrative centers or industrial clusters with significant numbers of employees, particularly in developing countries.

Appendix A. Main characteristics of the study scenario

Table A1. Main demographic characteristics of the cities of the study scenario

Characteristic	Group	Proportion			
		Santa Maria city	Cachoeira do Sul city	Frederico Westphalen city	Palmeira das Missões city
Gender	Male	47%	48%	45%	48%
	Female	53%	52%	55%	52%
Age (years)	16-29	34%	29%	35%	33%
	30-49	35%	34%	37%	36%
	50-64	24%	16%	17%	14%
	65 or more	7%	21%	11%	17%
Household net income (number of minimum wages)	< 2	24%	38%	25%	39%
	2-4	36%	37%	42%	37%
	> 4	37%	23%	31%	22%
	Unknown	3%	2%	2%	2%

Table A2. Sociodemographic distribution of the UFSM academic community

Characteristic	Group	Proportion
Gender	Male	45%
	Female	55%
Age (years)	16-29	67%
	30-49	26%
	50-64	6%
	65 or more	1%
Type	Student	87%
	Administration staff	7%
	Teacher	6%
Campus	Santa Maria	90%
	Cachoeira do Sul	3%
	Frederico Westphalen	3%
	Palmeira das Missões	4%
Household net income (number of minimum wages)	< 2	35%
	2-4	37%
	> 4	25%
	Unknown	3%

Appendix B. Detailed description of the measurement model

Based on the construct structure proposed for the identified attributes (see Table 1), the measurement model was analyzed using a CFA in which all the latent variables (constructs) were presented, with the possibility of covarying between them, but each observed variable (attribute) could only influence a single construct. It was previously confirmed that there was no collinearity between the observed variables and no outliers or missing values within the database obtained from the survey. Figure B1 shows the

initial structure considered for the specification and identification of the model. As shown in Figure B1, 28 indicators and 5 constructs were considered. Therefore, the model had 406 observations available and 66 parameters, resulting in 340 degrees of freedom.

Figure B1. Initial CFA measurement model

Table B1 presents the results of the initial measurement model, which converged to admissible solutions, and the corresponding adjustment parameters, confirming the constructs proposed from the attributes highlighted in the literature. The model failed the exact fit test, with $\chi^2(340) = 2,981.714$ ($p < 0.001$), so approximate model fit indices commonly used in the literature were considered, with acceptable RMSEA and SRMR values (lower than 0.08).

Table B1. Initial CFA measurement model results

	Unst.	SE	St.
<i>Bus_infra->bus_stop_lighting</i>	1.000	*	0.725
<i>Bus_infra->bus_stop_infra</i>	0.987	0.028	0.704
<i>Bus_infra->bus_stop_sidewalk</i>	0.935	0.031	0.655
<i>Bus_infra->bus_total_time</i>	0.933	0.032	0.672
<i>Bus_infra->bus_noise</i>	0.827	0.031	0.651
<i>Bus_oper->bus_availability</i>	1.000	*	0.687
<i>Bus_oper->bus_info</i>	0.927	0.033	0.646
<i>Bus_oper->bus_punctuality</i>	0.860	0.031	0.652
<i>Bus_oper->bus_payment</i>	0.677	0.033	0.510
<i>Bus_oper->bus_cost</i>	0.743	0.032	0.572
<i>Bus_oper->bus_comfort</i>	0.863	0.035	0.652

<i>Safety->bus_traffic_safety</i>	1.000	*	0.621
<i>Safety->bus_public_safety</i>	1.088	0.036	0.639
<i>Safety->geral_traffic_safety</i>	0.918	0.040	0.714
<i>Safety->geral_public_safety</i>	1.072	0.046	0.701
<i>Environment->geral_noise</i>	1.000	*	0.675
<i>Environment->geral_jam</i>	1.154	0.050	0.625
<i>Environment->geral_speed</i>	1.110	0.047	0.726
<i>Environment->geral_control</i>	1.149	0.049	0.699
<i>Foot_infra->public_lighting</i>	1.000	*	0.614
<i>Foot_infra->foot_accesib</i>	1.122	0.044	0.667
<i>Foot_infra->traffic_signs</i>	0.965	0.041	0.688
<i>Foot_infra->foot_ease</i>	1.195	0.046	0.812
<i>Foot_infra->foot_greenery</i>	1.054	0.052	0.582
<i>Foot_infra->sidewalk_infra</i>	1.178	0.045	0.823
<i>Foot_infra->sidewalk_width</i>	1.188	0.047	0.820
<i>Foot_infra->crosswalk_avail</i>	1.203	0.046	0.794
<i>Foot_infra->sidewalk_grad</i>	1.081	0.045	0.744
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Bus_infra)</i>	0.174	0.016	0.396
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Environment)</i>	0.244	0.018	0.684
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Bus_oper)</i>	0.198	0.017	0.443
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Safety)</i>	0.267	0.018	0.706
<i>cov(Bus_infra,Environment)</i>	0.265	0.017	0.588
<i>cov(Bus_infra,Bus_oper)</i>	0.489	0.024	0.867
<i>cov(Bus_infra,Safety)</i>	0.333	0.020	0.696
<i>cov(Environment,Bus_oper)</i>	0.254	0.018	0.554
<i>cov(Environment,Safety)</i>	0.306	0.018	0.786
<i>cov(Bus_oper,Safety)</i>	0.316	0.021	0.648
Model's fit statistics (Satorra-Bentler estimation)			
df (sb)	340		
chi-square (sb)	2,981.714		
p-value	0.000		
RMSEA (sb)	0.068		
CFI (sb)	0.860		
TLI (sb)	0.844		
SRMR	0.067		
AIC	109,938.667		
BIC	110,447.467		

* Not tested for statistical significance. All other unstandardized estimates are statistically significant at $p < 0.001$

Table B1 also shows the factor loadings of the observed variables, which in the case of non-standardized values were all significant. In addition, the values of the loadings were all positive and higher than 0.50, with the majority even higher than 0.70 (convergent validity). The Cronbach's Alpha values obtained varied between 0.927 and 0.930 (all

higher than 0.90, indicating excellent values) and the Construct Reliability (CR) results varied between 0.776 and 0.911 (higher than 0.70), so the convergent validity of the constructs was considered satisfactory. In addition, the correlations between the latent variables were not high, with values between 0.396 and 0.867 (lower than 0.90, indicating discriminant validity).

Based on the results of the initial measurement model, the correlations between the measurement errors of the observed variables were analyzed and the CFA model was re-specified, including 4 correlations: (1) *public_lighting* and *foot_accessibility* in *Foot_infra*; (2) *bus_stop_lighting* and *bus_stop_infrastructure* in *Bus_infra*; (3) *bus_payment* and *bus_cost* in *Bus_oper*; and (4) *bus_traffic_safety* and *bus_public_safety* in *Safety*. Such correlations are logical, since they relate attributes that influence similar aspects, according to the literature (Berežný and Konečný, 2017; Dewi et al., 2018; De Witte et al., 2013; Gurrutxaga et al., 2017; Li et al. al., 2022; Rohani et al., 2013; Tsami and Nathanail, 2017; Vallejo-Borda et al., 2020). Figure B2 shows the final measurement model, while Table B2 presents the parameter estimation results and the fit indices.

Figure B2. Final CFA measurement model

Table B2. Final CFA measurement model results

Path / Fit index	Unst.	SE	St.
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>bus_stop_lighting</i>	1.000	*	0.665
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>bus_stop_infra</i>	0.982	0.030	0.643
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>bus_stop_sidewalk</i>	0.992	0.034	0.638
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>bus_total_time</i>	1.045	0.036	0.691
<i>Bus_infra</i> -> <i>bus_noise</i>	0.922	0.034	0.667
<i>Bus_oper</i> -> <i>bus_availability</i>	1.000	*	0.691
<i>Bus_oper</i> -> <i>bus_info</i>	0.921	0.032	0.646

<i>Bus_oper->bus_punctuality</i>	0.862	0.030	0.658
<i>Bus_oper->bus_payment</i>	0.641	0.033	0.485
<i>Bus_oper->bus_cost</i>	0.710	0.031	0.550
<i>Bus_oper->bus_comfort</i>	0.857	0.033	0.651
<i>Safety->bus_traffic_safety</i>	1.000	*	0.515
<i>Safety->bus_public_safety</i>	1.085	0.045	0.529
<i>Safety->geral_traffic_safety</i>	1.199	0.059	0.774
<i>Safety->geral_public_safety</i>	1.372	0.068	0.745
<i>Environment->geral_noise</i>	1.000	*	0.680
<i>Environment->geral_jam</i>	1.144	0.049	0.623
<i>Environment->geral_speed</i>	1.103	0.046	0.727
<i>Environment->geral_control</i>	1.132	0.048	0.694
<i>Foot_infra->public_lighting</i>	1.000	*	0.604
<i>Foot_infra->foot_accesib</i>	1.123	0.045	0.657
<i>Foot_infra->traffic_signs</i>	0.980	0.042	0.687
<i>Foot_infra->foot_ease</i>	1.218	0.048	0.814
<i>Foot_infra->foot_greenery</i>	1.073	0.054	0.582
<i>Foot_infra->sidewalk_infra</i>	1.201	0.047	0.825
<i>Foot_infra->sidewalk_width</i>	1.212	0.049	0.823
<i>Foot_infra->crosswalk_avail</i>	1.225	0.048	0.796
<i>Foot_infra->sidewalk_grad</i>	1.099	0.046	0.744
<i>cov(e.public_lighting,e.foot_accesib)</i>	0.120	0.015	0.210
<i>cov(e.bus_stop_lighting,e.bus_stop_infra)</i>	0.221	0.019	0.361
<i>cov(e.bus_payment,e.bus_cost)</i>	0.161	0.020	0.222
<i>cov(e.bus_traffic_safety,e.bus_public_safety)</i>	0.396	0.020	0.480
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Bus_infra)</i>	0.174	0.016	0.396
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Environment)</i>	0.244	0.018	0.678
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Bus_oper)</i>	0.198	0.017	0.441
<i>cov(Foot_infra,Safety)</i>	0.267	0.018	0.738
<i>cov(Bus_infra,Environment)</i>	0.265	0.017	0.612
<i>cov(Bus_infra,Bus_oper)</i>	0.489	0.024	0.911
<i>cov(Bus_infra,Safety)</i>	0.333	0.020	0.609
<i>cov(Environment,Bus_oper)</i>	0.254	0.018	0.552
<i>cov(Environment,Safety)</i>	0.306	0.018	0.813
<i>cov(Bus_oper,Safety)</i>	0.316	0.021	0.552

Model's fit statistics (Satorra-Bentler estimation)

df (sb)	336
chi-square (sb)	2,434.305
p-value	0.000
RMSEA (sb)	0.061
CFI (sb)	0.885
TLI (sb)	0.875
SRMR	0.069
AIC	109,286.341

* Not tested for statistical significance. All other unstandardized estimates are statistically significant at $p < 0.001$

The parameter estimates were above 0.5 in all cases (except for *bus_payment*, but with a very close value). Most of the approximate fit indices improved, remaining acceptable (since the final CFA model also failed the exact fit test, with $\chi^2(336) = 2,434.305$ ($p < 0.001$)).

Appendix C. Detailed description of structural regression models

Once the measurement model showed satisfactory results, structural regression models were proposed for the relationships between the perceptions of the academic community regarding the attributes of urban mobility, safety, and the environment, with the aim of identifying ways to promote sustainable transport by bus for their journeys to the university. The tests started from a structural model including all the plausible relationships, according to the literature, among the constructs evaluated in the measurement model (see Figure C1.a), such that the perceptions of the users about the environment in which their journeys occurred were influenced by all the other latent variables. In addition, the public transport infrastructure was related to the environment by means of the mediation of perceptions about the infrastructure for walking and safety, which was also a mediator between the operation of public transport and the environment. Finally, the perception of the attributes related to pedestrian mobility was also influenced by the perceptions of the various safety aspects.

Figure C1. Structural regression models considered. (a) Initial model; (b) Final model.

According to the estimation results for the parameters of the initial model (Table C1), three relationships were not significant, namely those between *Bus_infra* and *Foot_infra*, between *Safety* and *Bus_oper*, and between *Bus_oper* and *Environment*.

Therefore, these relationships were eliminated to obtain the final model (Figure C1.b), for which the results were satisfactory, with all the significant relationships among the constructs. In this case, the parameter estimates were consistent, so the approximate fit indices and the ability of the model to explain the behavior of the respondents were checked (Table 3 of the manuscript).

Table C1. Initial SEM considering all tested hypothesis.

MODEL / Path	Unst.	SE	St.
<i>Bus_infra -> Foot_infra</i>	-0.258	0.022	-0.031
<i>Safety->Foot_infra</i>	0.819	0.055	0.758
<i>Foot_infra->Environment</i>	0.195	0.043	0.185
<i>Bus_infra->Environment</i>	0.317	0.084	0.355
<i>Safety->Environment</i>	0.634	0.065	0.558
<i>Bus_oper->Environment</i>	-0.147	0.080	-0.168
<i>Bus_oper->Bus_infra</i>	0.888	0.036	0.910
<i>Bus_infra->Safety</i>	0.370	0.083	0.471
<i>Bus_oper->Safety</i>	0.108	0.080	0.140

All unstandardized estimates are statistically significant at $p < 0.001$, except the values in bold

Acknowledgments

The first author thanks the CNPQ (Process 310258/2021-9) for the financial support.

References

- Allen, J., Muñoz, J. C., Ortúzar, J. D., 2018. Modelling service-specific and global transit satisfaction under travel and user heterogeneity. *Transportation Research Part A* 113, 509–528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2018.05.009>
- Balsas, C. J. L., 2003. Sustainable transportation planning on college campuses. *Transport Policy*, v. 10, n. 2003, p. 35-49. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0967-070X\(02\)00028-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0967-070X(02)00028-8)
- Bhat, C. R., Sardesai, R., 2006. Development of an Urban Accessibility Index. Research Report Number 4938-4. Center for Transportation Research Bureau of Engineering Research.
- Berežný, R., Konečný, V., 2017. The Impact of the Quality of Transport Services on Passenger Demand in the Suburban Bus Transport. *Procedia Engineering*, 192, 40–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.06.007>
- Cafiso, S., Di Graziano, A., Pappalardo, G., 2013. Using the Delphi method to evaluate opinions of public transport managers on bus safety. *Safety Science*, 57, 254–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.03.001>
- De Oña, 2020. The role of involvement with public transport in the relationship between service quality, satisfaction and behavioral intentions. *Transportation Research Part A* 142, 296–318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2020.11.006>
- dell’Olio, L., Ibeas, A., Cecín, P., 2010. Modelling user perception of bus transit quality. *Transport Policy*, 17(6), 388–397. doi:10.1016/j.tranpol.2010.04.006

- De Witte, A., Hollevoet, J., Dobruszkes, F., Hubert, M., Macharis, C., 2013. Linking modal choice to motility: A comprehensive review. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 49, 329–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2013.01.009>
- Dewi, D. I. K., Rakhmatulloh, A. R., Anggraini, P., 2018. Mapping between Bus Rapid Transit Shelter and High School Location in Semarang. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 123, 012013. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/123/1/012013>
- Fontoura, W. B., Chaves, G. L. D., Ribeiro, G. M., 2019. The Brazilian urban mobility policy: The impact in São Paulo transport system using system dynamics. *Transport Policy*, v. 73, p. 51-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2018.09.014>
- Gurrutxaga, I., Iturrate, M., Osés, U., Garcia, H., 2017. Analysis of the modal choice of transport at the case of university: Case of University of the Basque Country of San Sebastian. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, v. 105, p. 233-244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2017.04.003>
- Guzman, L. A., Arellana, J., Alvarez, V., 2020. Confronting congestion in urban areas: Developing Sustainable Mobility Plans for public and private organizations in Bogotá. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, v. 134, p. 321-335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2020.02.019>
- Hamad, K., Htun, P. T. T., Obaid, L., 2021. Characterization of travel behavior at a university campus: A case study of Sharjah University City, UAE. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 12, 100488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100488>
- Harbering, M., Schlüter, J., 2020. Determinants of transport mode choice in metropolitan areas the case of the metropolitan area of the Valley of Mexico. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 87 (July 2019), 102766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2020.102766>
- Hickman, R., Hall, P., Banister, D., 2013. Planning more for sustainable mobility. *Journal of Transport Geography*, v. 33, p. 210-219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2013.07.004>
- IBGE, 2021. Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics. Estimated population (Estimates of the resident population with reference date July 1st, 2021). Available at: <https://www.ibge.gov.br/estatisticas/sociais/populacao/9103-estimativas-de-populacao.html> [in Portuguese].
- Kline, R. B., 2015. *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling*. 4th edition. New York, NY. 445 p.
- Ko, J., Lee, S., Byun, M., 2019. Exploring factors associated with commute mode choice: An application of city-level general social survey data. *Transport Policy* 75, 36-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2018.12.007>
- Li, L., Gao, T., Yu, L., Zhang, Y., 2022. Applying an integrated approach to metro station satisfaction evaluation: A case study in Shanghai, China. *International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology* 11, 780–789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijtst.2021.10.004>
- Limanond, T., Butsingorn, T., Chermkhunthod, C., 2011. Travel behavior of university students who live on campus: A case study of a rural university in Asia. *Transport Policy*, 18(1), 163-171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2010.07.006>
- Maia, A. G., de Carvalho, C. S., Venancio, L. C., Dini, E. D., 2020. The Motives Behind Transport Mode Choice: a Study with University Students in Brazil. *Ambiente e Sociedade*, 23, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-4422asoc20170188r4vu2020L5AO>
- Miralles-Guasch, C., Domene, E., 2010. Sustainable transport challenges in a suburban university: The case of the Autonomous University of Barcelona. *Transport Policy*, v. 17, n. 6, p. 454–463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2010.04.012>
- Nash, S., Mitra, R., 2019. University students' transportation patterns, and the role of neighbourhood types and attitudes. *Journal of Transport Geography*, v. 76, p. 200-211.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2019.03.013>

- Noor, H. M., Nasrudin, N., Foo, J., 2014. Determinants of Customer Satisfaction of Service Quality: City Bus Service in Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 153, 595–605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.10.092>
- Oestreich, L., Rhoden, P. S., Vieira, J. S., Ruiz-Padillo, A., 2023. Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the profile and preferences of urban mobility in Brazil: Challenges and opportunities. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 31, 312–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2023.01.002>
- Orellana, D., Bustos, M.E., Marín-Palacios, M., Cabrera-Jara, N., & Hermida, M.A., 2020. Walk'n'roll: Mapping street-level accessibility for different mobility conditions in Cuenca. Ecuador. *Journal of Transport & Health* 16, 100821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2020.100821>
- Rohani, M. M., Wijeyesekera, D. C., Karim, A. T. A., 2013. Bus operation, quality service and the role of bus provider and driver. *Procedia Engineering*, 53, 167–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2013.02.022>
- Ruiz-Padillo, A., Oestreich, L., Torres, T.B., Rhoden, P.S., Larranaga, A.M., Cybis, H.B., 2022. Weighted assessment of barriers to walking in small cities: A Brazilian case. *Transportation Research Part D* 109, 103392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2022.103392>
- Sakellariou, A., Kotoula, K.M., Morfoulaki, M., Mintsis, G., 2017. Identification of quality indexes in school bus transportation system. *Transportation Research Procedia* 24, 212–219.
- Santoso, D. S., Yajima, M., Sakamoto, K., Kubota, H., 2012. Opportunities and strategies for increasing bus ridership in rural Japan: A case study of Hidaka City. *Transport Policy*, 24, 320–329.
- Soria-Lara, J. A., Marquet, O., Miralles-Guasch, C., 2017. The influence of location, socioeconomics, and behaviour on travel-demand by car in metropolitan university campuses. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 53, 149–160. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.04.008>
- Soza-Parra, J., Raveau, S., Muñoz, J. C., 2022. Public transport reliability across preferences, modes, and space. *Transportation* 49(2), 621–640. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-021-10188-2>
- Stein, P. P., Rodrigues da Silva, A. N., 2018. Barriers, motivators and strategies for sustainable mobility at the USP campus in São Carlos, Brazil. *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, v. 6, n. 3, p. 329-335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2017.11.007>
- Tavares, V.B., Lucchesi, S.T., Larranaga, A.M., Cybis, H.B.B., 2021. Influence of public transport quality attributes on user satisfaction of different age cohorts. *Case Studies on Transport Policy* 9, 1042–1050. doi:10.1016/j.cstp.2021.04.018.
- Tsami, M., Nathanail, E., 2017. Guidance Provision for Increasing Quality of Service of Public Transport. *Procedia Engineering*, 178, 551–557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.01.108>
- UFSM, 2021. UFSM in numbers. Available at: <https://portal.ufsm.br/ufsm-em-numeros/publico/index.html>
- Vallejo-Borda, J. A., Cantillo, V., Rodriguez-Valencia, A., 2020. A perception-based cognitive map of the pedestrian perceived quality of service on urban sidewalks. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 73, 107-118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2020.06.013>
- Villaveces, A., Nieto, L. A., Ortega, D., Ríos, J. F., Medina, J. J., Gutiérrez, M. I., Rodríguez, D., 2012. Pedestrians' perceptions of walkability and safety in relation to the built environment in Cali, Colombia, 2009–10. *Injury Prevention*, 18(5), 291–297. <https://doi.org/10.1136/injuryprev-2011-040223>
- Whalen, K. E., Páez, A., Carrasco, J. A., 2013. Mode choice of university students commuting to school and the role of active travel. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 31, 132–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2013.06.008>

- Yilmaz, V., Ari, E., 2017. The effects of service quality, image and customer satisfaction on customer complain and loyalty in high speed rail service in Turkey: A proposal of the structural equation model. *Transportmetrica A: Transport Science*, 13, 67-90. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/23249935.2016.1209255>
- Zannat, K. E.; Adnan, Mo. S. G.; Dewan, A., 2020. A GIS-based approach to evaluating environmental influences on active and public transport accessibility of university students. *Journal of Urban Management*, v. 9, n. 3, p. 331-346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jum.2020.06.001>
- Zhan, G., Yan, X., Zhu, S., Wang, Y., 2016. Using hierarchical tree-based regression model to examine university student travel frequency and mode choice patterns in China. *Transport Policy*, v. 45, p. 55-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2015.09.006>